

Contemplation in the *Decem libri* of Felip Ribot (ca. 1370)

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Introduction

The *Decem libri de institutione et peculiaribus gestis religiosorum carmelitarum* is a complex work in multiple parts, attributed to several different authors, in redactional layers now difficult to disentangle.¹ Its present form was given it by Felip Ribot (†1391), Carmelite prior provincial of Catalonia. In all but three of the ten surviving manuscripts it is dated 1370, though perhaps it did not circulate widely until some decades later.²

Ribot claims to have contributed little of his own to the *Decem libri*, which he presents as a compilation of previously-existing works, the earliest supposedly a translation of a Greek original from the fourth century and the latest from the thirteenth, and he claims that he has clearly indicated the interpolations of which he is the author. The truth, I believe, lies somewhere between here and the assumption of many scholars that he is the single author of the whole work.³ Taken as a whole, the *Decem libri* provides a symbolic-legendary history of the Order from its origin in the prophet Elijah and the sons of the prophets until its expulsion from the Holy Land in 1291 and its transformation into a mendicant order.

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¹For the sake of clarity I use *Decem libri* to refer to the Ribot collection as a whole, and *Liber de institutione* for the work attributed under this title to John, forty-fourth bishop of Jerusalem, which stretches over the first seven of the ten books; this part is also commonly called *The Book of the First Monks*. As Ribot presents a compilation of various works, there are various titles for its various parts: in the Prologue the whole is entitled *Decem libri de institutione et peculiaribus gestis religiosorum carmelitarum*; its explicit is at 10.8. Books 1–7 are presented as a separate work: its incipit (1.1) reads: *Iohannes xliiii episcopus ierosolimitanus in libro de institutione primorum monachorum in lege ueteri exortorum et in noua perseuerantium ad Caprasium monachum*, and it has a separate explicit at 7.8. Book 1, almost certainly a pre-existing work, also has a separate explicit at 1.8. Incipits and explicits are often abbreviated and not free of textual variants. The other component works attributed to different authors have titles but not incipits.

²Francesc Martí, a successor to Ribot as provincial of Catalonia, provided a copy to the *studium generale* in Paris (now Bibliothèque de l’Arsenal, ms 779), as noted on f. 85v. The gift is probably to be dated between 1380 and 1398, between his inception as master and his election as provincial; cf. Paul Chandler, “The *Liber de institutione et peculiaribus gestis religiosorum carmelitarum ad Caprasium monachum* by Felip Ribot, O.Carm. (d. 1390): A Critical Edition with an Introduction,” Ph.D. thesis (University of Toronto, 1991), liv–lviii. See also Valerie Edden, “Felip Ribot’s *Institution of the First Monks*: Telling Stories About the Carmelites,” *Journal of the Early Book Society for the Study of Manuscripts and Printing History* 7 (2004): 141–51 at 142. A copy seems not to have arrived in England until after 1420/21, when the provincial, Thomas Netter, wrote twice to the prior general requesting one; cf. *Epp.* 27 and 28 in *Monumenta Historica Carmelitana*, ed. Benedict Zimmerman (Lérins: Ex typis abbatiae, 1905–7), 461, 464.

³A position expressed most strongly by Richard Copsey in “Establishment, Identity and Papal Approval: The Carmelite Order’s Creation of Its Legendary History,” *Carmelus* 47 (2000): 41–53 at 52; and in Felip Ribot, *The Ten Books on the Way of Life and Great Deeds of the Carmelites*, ed. and trans. Richard Copsey, Early Carmelite Spirituality, vol. 1 (Faversham: Saint Albert’s Press, 2005), xiii–xiv. See further in note 44 below. Ribot’s own vocabulary for his work deserves more consideration than it has so far received: *conficere, annectere, inserere, edere, compingere*.

While there is little in the work which is absolutely original, it provided a definitive and influential synthesis of the varied traditions and legends about the Order's foundation and its relationship to the prophet Elijah and the Virgin Mary which had been developing since the beginning of the community and in writing from the 1240s.⁴

In 1956 Rudolf Hendriks, basing himself on the small corpus of surviving literature about their identity produced by medieval Carmelites themselves, asserted that their legends about Elijah were created in Europe and dated back no earlier than the 1280s, and numerous authors have followed him until the present.⁵ After more than sixty years this erroneous claim should be retired. In fact, the earliest evidence for the relationship of the Carmelites to Elijah, and also to the Virgin Mary, is much earlier, of Palestinian origin, and comes from witnesses outside the Order. For the association with Elijah there is eyewitness evidence from about 1220 in chapter 52 of the *Historia orientalis* of Jacques de Vitry, bishop of nearby Acre, which notes that the hermits of Mount Carmel lived there “ad exemplum et imitationem sancti viri et solitarii Elie prophete”.⁶ For Mary there is early evidence from the reports in pilgrim itineraries of the patronal chapel dedicated to her on Mount Carmel, e.g., *Citez de Jerusalem* (ca. 1220-1229) and *Les sains pelerinages* (ca. 1250),⁷ and also in papal documents from the 1240s on.⁸

Through these foundational traditions medieval Carmelites had sought to express their spiritual identity, generally by using forms of symbolic narrative. As in many processes of contemporary legend-making, 13th- and 14th-century Carmelites expressed their spiritual values in narratives projected back into a mythical past. This is a less unusual process than is often assumed: the Knights Hospitaller, for example, created legends in the mid-12th century which traced the Hospital back to biblical times: to the Maccabees; to Jesus himself, who was supposed to have done healing miracles there; to the Virgin Mary and the disciples living there after the Ascension; and to Saint Stephen the Protomartyr, whom they claimed as the first master of the Order.⁹ But the Carmelites embraced their legends with a striking and

⁴Most of these Carmelite works have been edited by Adrianus Staring, *Medieval Carmelite Heritage: Early Reflections on the Nature of the Order*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana, vol. 16 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1989). There is now broad agreement that the *Rubrica prima* of the first surviving constitutions (1281), a sort of primordial statement of the Order's claim to foundation by the Prophet Elijah, dates back to the 1240s or even earlier; Ludovico Saggi, “Agiografia carmelitana,” in *Santi del Carmelo* (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1972), 25–26; Carlo Cicconetti, *La Regola del Carmelo: origine, natura, significato*, Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana, vol. 12 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1973), 89–92; Staring, *MCH*, 33–37.

⁵“La succession héréditaire (1280-1451)”, in *Élie le prophète*, (Paris: Desclée de Brouwer, 1956), 2:34-81.

⁶*Histoire orientale = Historia orientalis*, introduction, édition critique et traduction par Jean Donnadieu, Sous la règle de saint Augustin (Turnhout: Brepols, 2008), 218–220. On the date see C. Cannuyer, “Le date de rédaction de l'*Historia orientalis* de Jacques de Vitry 1160/70–1240, évêque d'Acre,” *Revue d'Histoire Ecclésiastique* 78 (1983): 65–72, who suggests 1220; and Jean Donnadieu, “L'*Historia orientalis* de Jacques de Vitry: tradition manuscrite et histoire du texte,” *Sacris Erudiri* 45 (2006): 379–456, who prefers a range between 1216 and 1223. On the history and development of the Elijan legend in Carmel see Ludovico Saggi's seminal essay “Agiografia carmelitana”, in *Santi del Carmelo*, (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1972), 23-108; and further in Cosmas Peters, et al., “Elia profeta”, *ibid.*, 136–153.

⁷*Itinera Hierosolymitana Crucesignatorum saec. XII-XIII*, ed. Sabino de Sandoli, 4 vols, (Jerusalem: Pubblicazioni dello Studium Biblicum Franciscanum, 1978-1984), 3:450 and 2:142.

⁸Cf. Emanuele Boaga, “Una lettera ‘secreta’ di Innocenzo IV a favore dei Carmelitani,” *Analecta Ordinis Carmelitarum* 41 (1990): 107–11; and Nilo Geagea, *Maria, Madre e Decoro del Carmelo: La pietà mariana dei Carmelitani durante i tre primi secoli della loro storia*, Institutum Historicum Teresianum: Studia 4 (Rome: Teresianum, 1988), 94–109.

⁹Antoine Calvet, *Les légendes de l'Hôpital de Saint-Jean de Jérusalem: textes, traductions, notes*

long-lasting intensity and an unusual preference for narrative over other genres of spiritual discourse.

The traditions which Ribot inherited were not entirely consistent, and it was his great achievement to bring them together with a unity of conception and a spiritual coherence which makes his work the first synthetic exposition of the characteristic spirituality of the Order. Many of its great themes are brought together here (transformation in Christ, purity of heart, openness to the Word, silence and solitude, the centrality of love, liturgical prayer, the building of a peaceful and loving community, etc.), and many of its great symbols (Elijah and Mary, Mount Carmel, Carith, the chapel in the midst, the habit, the journey, etc.).

Reading the work fruitfully requires taking account of its complex and sophisticated structure, which is both a portrait of the Order's self-understanding and spirituality and an invitation to the reader to enter into the spiritual journey. It returns repeatedly to the same themes from different directions, or under different symbols, or as part of different aspects of the Carmelite story. The end result is a tightly constructed work in which the parts contain the whole.

The explicit vocabulary of contemplation is comparatively rare in the *Liber de institutione*. I count twenty-one occurrences of *contemplatio* and its cognates in roughly 40,000 words, and of these seven are references to 1 Kings 18:43, where *contemplatus* simply means "looked",¹⁰ two perhaps have the generic sense of "consider", and three are in quotations from other writers.

In this paper I wish to propose that the discourse of contemplation is nevertheless central to the *Decem libri* and to Ribot's vision of the spirituality and history of the Order, and that his vision suggests that "contemplation" should to be considered in a broad sense. I want to propose some sketches about how contemplation might be understood in this work: they are by way of hypotheses which might be further tested against the Ribot collection and other texts of the Carmelite tradition.

1) *Contemplation is a process of spiritual transformation*

The first book of the *Decem libri*, almost certainly from an older non-Carmelite source,¹¹ is a lengthy allegorical commentary on the text of 1 Kings 17:2-4, God's command to the prophet Elijah:

Depart from here, and go towards the east, and hide in the wadi Carith, which is over against the Jordan, and there you will drink of the torrent, and I have commanded the ravens to feed you there.

In its mystical sense, this text—which becomes the template for the allegorically interpreted life of Elijah—is said to contain the pattern (*forma*) for arriving at the perfection of the

et commentaires, Centre d'Enseignement et de Recherche d'Oc, vol. 11 (Paris: Presses de l'Université de Paris Sorbonne, 2000); Sylvia Schein, "The *Miracula* of the Hospital of St. John and the Carmelite Elianic Tradition," in *Cross Cultural Convergences in the Crusader Period: Essays Presented to Aryeh Grabois on His Sixtieth Birthday*, ed. Michael Goodich, Sophia Menache, and Sylvia Schein (New York: Peter Lang, 1995), 287–96; J.C.S. Riley-Smith, *The Knights of St John in Jerusalem and Cyprus, c. 1050–1310* (London: Macmillan, 1967), 32–59.

¹⁰ "Et dixit [Helias] ad puerum suum, ascende et prospice contra mare; qui cum ascendisset et contemplatus esset, ait, non est quicquam." ("And he said to his servant: Go up, and look toward the sea. And he went up, and looked, and said: There is nothing." [Douay-Rheims]).

¹¹ While Mount Carmel is the foundational holy place of Carmelite self-conception and even of the name of the Order, in Book 1 it is the wadi Carith where Elijah begins the eremitical way of life. The difficulty this poses requires a later chapter (3.1) to explain why the Carmelites are not called "Carithites" after their place of foundation.

prophetic-eremital life which is followed by Elijah's disciples, the ancient sons of the prophets, and also by the Carmelites of Ribot's own time. In the most-quoted passage of the work, the Carmelite way of life is explained as follows:

The goal of this life is twofold. One part we acquire by our own effort and the exercise of the virtues, with the help of divine grace. This is to offer God a heart that is holy and pure from all actual stain of sin. We attain this goal when we are perfect and 'in Carith', that is, hidden in that charity of which the Wise Man says: 'Love covers all offences' (Proverbs 10:12). Wishing Elijah to reach this goal, God said to him, 'Hide in the wadi Carith'.

The other goal of this life is granted to us as the sheer gift of God: namely, not only after death but already in this mortal life, to taste somewhat in the heart and to experience in the mind the power of the divine presence and the sweetness of heavenly glory. This is to drink of the torrent of the pleasure of God. God promised this end to Elijah in the words, 'And there you shall drink of the torrent' (1 Kings 17:4; cf. Psalm 109:7) (1.2).¹²

This important passage is dependent on a similarly key passage from John Cassian's Conference 14, which draws in turn from the spiritual theology of Evagrius Ponticus:

This is indeed a twofold knowledge: the first is *praktiké*, or practical, which is achieved in the reformation of morals and the purgation of vices; the second is *theoretiké*, which consists in the contemplation of divine realities and the understanding of most sacred meanings. Whoever, therefore, wishes to attain to *theoretiké* must first pursue practical knowledge with all his strength and power, for the *praktiké* can be possessed without the theoretical, but the theoretical cannot in any way be attained without the practical.¹³

The first goal, purity of heart, a synonym for holiness, is Cassian's translation of Evagrius' *apatheia*, the *skopos* or immediate aim of the monastic life, to which all the ascetical practices of monasticism—fasting, vigils, prayer, solitude, silence, and the rest—are in service.¹⁴ The second goal, the anticipation of future beatitude and the foretaste of the divine presence, corresponds to Cassian's *telos* or *destinatio*, the ultimate goal of monastic life, the Kingdom of God.¹⁵

Through the first of these, that is through purity of heart and perfection of love, one comes to the second, namely to an experiential knowledge of the divine power and heavenly glory. As the Lord says, 'He who loves me will be loved by my Father, and I will love him and will show myself to him' (John 14:21) (1.2).

The influence of Cassian in the programmatic statement of this chapter of the *Liber de institutione* is direct and striking, and conditions the rest of the book. Its notion of contemplation, then, needs to be understood in the basic structure of the spiritual theology of Evagrius as mediated to the West by Cassian, and in the general context of the monastic spirituality of the fourth century.¹⁶ It also needs to be considered in the light of the 12th-

¹² I will make references to the *Decem libri* parenthetically in the text in the form 2.1 (book.chapter). The translation is my own, and the Latin text from my forthcoming critical edition.

¹³ John Cassian, *Conference 14.1-2*; *Conférences*, ed. E. Pichery, Sources Chrétiennes, 3 vols, (Paris: Éditions du Cerf, 1955–59), 54:183–184.

¹⁴ Cf. Cassian, *Conf.* 1.5.3; SC 42:82. On Evagrian *apatheia* cf. Jeremy Driscoll, *Steps to Spiritual Perfection: Studies in Spiritual Progress in Evagrius Ponticus* (New York: Newman Press, 2005), 76–93; Columba Stewart, *Cassian the Monk*, Oxford Studies in Historical Theology (New York: Oxford University Press, 1998), esp. 40–47.

¹⁵ Cassian, *Conf.* 10.7; SC 54:81–82. On the links between Evagrius' and Cassian's views of the goal of monastic life, cf. Stewart, *Cassian the Monk*, 38–39.

¹⁶ See especially Bernard McGinn, *The Foundations of Mysticism: Origins to the Fifth Century*, The Presence of God: A History of Western Christian Mysticism, vol. 1 (New York: Crossroad, 1991). Also

century revival of interest in the Desert Fathers, particularly in eremitical circles emerging in the long wake of the Gregorian Reform,¹⁷ of which we may consider the Carmelites one of the last institutional expressions. We have not yet explored sufficiently how and if the emerging Carmelite tradition might also reflect the systematising spirituality of the Victorines in the 12th century, or later be adapted to the currents that led to Jean Gerson's works in the 15th, and these would be useful explorations to make.

It seems to me that the influence of Cassian in the *Liber de institutione* is so marked—of course, it is presented to the reader as a fourth-century composition—that we might consider it a deliberately archaising work, reflecting the concern of 12th-century religious movements to root innovation in an appeal to the pristine traditions of the early church and the earliest monasticism.¹⁸

In the tradition drawn from Evagrius and Cassian, the *Liber de institutione* sees contemplation as the core of a continuous process of spiritual transformation in which human effort and divine grace intersect. In the systematic presentation of the spiritual journey in Book 1, this transformation is launched in four steps, a series of renunciations which lead to ever-deeper layers of purification of the self and to growing spiritual freedom. There is space here only to summarise.

Each of the steps is presented as an allegorisation of a successive phrase in the text of 1 Kings 17:2-4. However, it is Christ who speaks as the mentor of the process, “turning an objective statement into a personal message from Jesus to his beloved”.¹⁹ Christ urges his disciple to perfection, and gradually and paradoxically the life of the Old Testament prophet is revealed as one of evangelical values and of identification with Christ:

- 1) *Depart from here* (1.3)
Renunciation of earthly things
Purification: of relationships to things
= Poverty

Stewart, *Cassian the Monk, passim*; *Evagrius Ponticus*, ed. A. M. Casiday (New York: Routledge, 2006); William Harmless, *Desert Christians: An Introduction to the Literature of Early Monasticism* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004), 311–409; *idem, Mystics* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 135–57.

¹⁷ Bernard McGinn, *The Growth of Mysticism: Gregory the Great Through the 12th Century*, The Presence of God, vol. 2 (New York: Crossroad, 1994); Henrietta Leyser, *Hermits and the New Monasticism: A Study of Religious Communities in Western Europe 1000–1150*, New Studies in Medieval History (London: Macmillan Press, 1984); Giles Constable, *The Reformation of the Twelfth Century* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996); Lin Donnat, “La spiritualité du désert au XIIe siècle,” *Collectanea Cisterciensia* 53 (1991): 146–56; *L'eremitismo in Occidente nei secoli XI e XII*, Atti della seconda settimana internazionale di studio, Mendola, 30 agosto-6 settembre 1962, Miscellanea del Centro di Studi Medioevali, vol. 4 (Milan: Vita e Pensiero, 1965). For the 14th century cf. Eric L. Saak, “*Ex vita patrum formatur vita fratrum*: The Appropriation of the Desert Fathers in the Augustinian Monasticism of the Later Middle Ages,” *Church History and Religious Culture* 86 (2006): 191–228.

¹⁸ Glenn Olsen, “The Idea of the *Ecclesia Primitiva* in the Writings of the Twelfth-Century Canonists,” *Traditio* 25 (1969): 61–86; Beryl Smalley, “Ecclesiastical Attitudes to Novelty, c. 1100-c. 1250,” in *Church, Society and Politics*, ed. Derek Baker, Studies in Church History, vol. 12, (Oxford: Blackwell, 1975), 113–131; Giles Constable, “Renewal and Reform in Religious Life: Concepts and Realities,” in *Renaissance and Renewal in the Twelfth Century*, ed. Robert L. Benson and Giles Constable (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1982), 37–67; Giles Constable, “L’idea di innovazione nel XII secolo,” in *Il secolo XII: La “renovation” dell’Europa cristiana. Atti della XLIII settimana di studio, Trento, 11–15 settembre 2000*, ed. Giles Constable, et al., Annali Dell’Istituto Storico Italiano-Germanico in Trento: Quaderni, vol. 62 (Bologna: Istituto trentino di cultura, 2003), 327–36.

¹⁹ Valerie Edden, “‘The Prophetycal Lyf of an Heremyte’: Elijah as the Model of the Contemplative Life in The Book of the First Monks,” in *The Medieval Mystical Tradition in England: Exeter Symposium VII: Papers Read at Charney Manor, July 2004*, ed. E.A. Jones (Cambridge: Brewer, 2004), 152.

Freedom: *from* competing desires, *for* hearing the word of God

2) *Go eastward* (1.4)

Renunciation: of sin and self-will

Purification: of relationship to one's inner motives

= Obedience

Freedom: *from* egocentricity, *for* conformity to Christ, obedient to death

3) *Hide in the wadi Carith* (1.5)

Renunciation: of marriage and the city (the place of injustice) for silence and solitude in the desert, which creates attentiveness to grace and thirst for salvation

Purification: of relationships to others

= Chastity

Freedom: *from* injustice, *for* an undivided heart, transformed relationships to God and others

4) *Which is over against the Jordan* (1.6)

Renunciation: of sin (as the opposite of love)

Purification: of the "whole heart"

= Integration

Freedom: *from* sin; *for* love of God, self, and neighbour with the whole heart

These four "steps" (*gradus*), perhaps better thought of as a spiral of intersecting processes of progressive purification, correspond to the *praktiké* of Evagrius and the *puritas cordis* of Cassian, so influential in all subsequent spirituality.²⁰ They are the result of ascetical effort. The *Liber de institutione*, however, is not much interested in ascetical practices as such, of which it has virtually nothing to say, but rather of the inner personal transformation which these practices are designed to foster, and of their aim, which is growth in that love which is the gospel commandment (Matthew 10:37, Luke 14:26, quoted in 1.6). The purpose of all this training is "the love which springs from a pure heart and a good conscience and sincere faith" (1.7, quoting 1 Timothy 1:5). Love alone restores us to the image and likeness of God in which we were created and from which we have fallen (1.6). These purificatory processes which re-orient the person to God must be continued at ever-deeper levels of the self, so that one passes from being *in Carith/in caritate* to being "hidden" in Carith/in charity: this requires a long apprenticeship.²¹

But remember that before I said to you 'And there you will drink of the torrent', I said 'Hide in the wadi Carith'. I said this first because in order to drink spiritually of the torrent you must first

²⁰ See esp. *Purity of Heart in Early Ascetic and Monastic Literature: Essays in Honor of Juana Raasch, O.S.B.*, ed. Harriet Luckman and Linda Kulzer (Collegeville, Minn.: Liturgical Press, 1999).

²¹ The Latin pun *Carith/caritas*, constitutive for the spirituality of the work, indicates it was never in Greek, as claimed in the *Epistola Cyrilli*, 7.6 and 8.1–3 of the *Decem libri*. However, the presence in Carmelite writing of John, 44th bishop of Jerusalem, otherwise known as John II (d. 417), is a curious feature best explained as an early Carmelite tradition of Palestinian origin, as I have argued at greater length elsewhere (Chandler, "The *Liber de institutione*", xlvi-lv). He is already present in *Universis christifidelibus*, one of the earliest surviving works by a Carmelite author, dating probably from 1289 (Staring, *MCH*, 71–80). The Carmelite connection with John can hardly have been invented in the West, where John, remembered mainly as one condemned by Saints Jerome and Augustine, had no standing as an authoritative figure. In Palestine and the East, however, he was regarded as a saint, with a feast in the Jerusalem calendar since soon after his death (cf. A. Renoux, *Le codex arménien Jérusalem 121. I. Introduction*, in F. Graffin, ed., *Patrologia Orientalis* 35, (Turnhout: Brepols, 1970), 179-180, for a feast on 29 March). For general treatments of John see J.-M. Sauget, "Giovanni II, vescovo di Gerusalemme", in *Bibliotheca Sanctorum* 6 (1965) 931-934; and Daniel Stiernon, "Jean de Jérusalem", in *Dictionnaire de Spiritualité* 8 (1974) 565-574, with bibliography.

be hidden in Carith, that is in charity: and you will not be hidden there immediately when you first begin to be there because, as it is said, not just any charity but only perfect charity 'covers all offences' (Proverbs 10:12).

Even though as soon as you begin to love me with your whole heart you are truly 'in Carith', that is in charity, you are not immediately 'hidden in Carith', that is in charity, because you are not at once completely divided from all the actual cupidity of sin. For carnal passions and unclean thoughts are not soon quieted, indeed, they will surge up in you, trying to draw your heart to forbidden things and to withdraw you from my love entirely—and for this reason you are not yet able to love me perfectly 'with your whole heart'. And even though your heart from then on assiduously and habitually retains my love in itself, you are still not able to be brought to me peacefully and perfectly through actual love.

If you are so trained in my commands and counsels that you flee not only unclean thoughts and carnal passions contrary to my love but even other things which impede and retard the fervor of my love; and if you choose the things which favour my love so that from then you love me completely with such a heartfelt love and cling to me serenely with such powerful affection that in your mind you feel no desire contrary to my love or impeding it, then you are beginning to love me perfectly with all your heart and are 'hidden in Carith', that is in charity, and are on the way to your chosen goal. For 'the aim of the law is the love which comes from a pure heart and a good conscience and sincere faith' (1 Timothy 1:5).

Finally, the practitioner comes towards the goal of the monastic life:

There you shall drink of the torrent (1.7)

The experience of perfect love

Purification: is now through the active work of God

= Transformation

Freedom: *from* all egocentricity, *for* life in the Holy Spirit

Here the monk experiences that perfect purity of heart by which "a love may freely rise which is so fervent and powerful and yet so peaceful and complete in binding your heart to me without any resistance at all, that your heart feels nothing whatsoever in it contrary to my love or hindering it, but rests absolutely at peace in my love" (1.7). This tranquillity of spirit corresponds to Evagrius' *apatheia* and Cassian's purity of heart.²² It is enabled by the loss of all resistance to the work of grace, and its mode is what later writers will call passive, that is, it is a gift and not a work of human effort. "In this perfect union of yourself with me", Christ says, "I shall give you and your companions to drink from the torrent..." In a lyrical passage this pure love is described as

those inexpressible and sweet spiritual delights about which it is written: 'Eye has not seen, nor ear heard, neither has it entered into the heart of man, what God has prepared for those that love him' (1 Corinthians 2:9). These delights are called 'torrents' indeed, because with force like a torrent and with great abundance of pleasure they flood the mind of the prophet... These are indeed 'torrents of gold': they shine both with the ardour of the love of God from which they flow into the prophet's mind and with the manifest knowledge of God to which they secretly lead the prophetic person. As the Lord says: 'He that loves me, will be loved by my Father, and I will love him and show myself to him' (John 14:21)... [Y]our reward will be to enjoy an abundance of divine conversation, so that hidden and even future things will sometimes be revealed to you by God. Then 'you shall abound in unspeakable delights in the Almighty' and shall readily 'lift up the face' of your mind to contemplate God (cf. Job 22:23-26 [Vulgate]).²³

²² Cf. esp. Stewart, *Cassian the Monk*, 40–61.

²³ "Et elevabis ad Deum libere contemplantum faciem mentis tuam": This is only the third occurrence of a cognate of *contemplatio* in the *Liber de institutione*, which is rather lacking in this specific vocabulary. The previous occurrences are at the beginning of 1.2 in a reference to Elijah ("obtentu contemplationis diuinae... profectus") drawn from Cassian, *Conf.* 18.6; SC 64:17; and in 1.4 in a

The arrival point of the monk at the “abundance of divine conversation” seems to me a literary inclusion with the departure point in 1.3, where the first step to perfection involves the renunciation of precisely those things which prevent listening to the word of God, and indeed suffocate the word (Mark 4:19, quoted there). In this sense, contemplation begins with being-addressed-by-God and is fulfilled in entry into intimate converse with God.

The intersecting dynamism of asceticism and contemplative experience of the divine presence has its counterpart in the death and resurrection of Christ, the dynamism of the Pauline mysticism of the paschal mystery, central to all Carmelite spirituality.²⁴ Renunciation and self-emptying are met by a transforming recompense. Contemplation is ultimately possible only through identification with Christ, whose poverty made him the perfect hearer of the word, whose obedience made him its perfect doer, and whose love made him its perfect incarnation. Contemplation requires—or perhaps is—an entry into the paschal mystery of death and resurrection.

The eighth and final chapter of Book 1 is most interesting. That it exists at all is significant in itself. If contemplation is the “perfection” of the monastic life (1.7), there should be nothing to follow. However, the contemplative experience of God is a mere glimpse and only transitory, for God lives in unapproachable light, and no-one can see him in this life. After contemplation, therefore, comes perseverance and deeper conversion, “forgetting the things that are behind and pressing on to those before” (Philippians 3.13):

I have commanded the ravens to feed you there (1.8)

Humble perseverance and unceasing prayer

Purification: a life-long commitment to conversion

= Recapitulation

Freedom: *from* proud elation in spiritual experience, *for* orientation to an infinite future

These ideas are developed through a fable, common in medieval bestiaries and ultimately drawn from Gregory the Great and Isidore of Seville, about ravens, who are supposedly born white and not fed by their mothers until they develop black feathers.²⁵ They represent the prophets, who are fed with the word of God only when they acknowledge themselves as the blackest of sinners.

The contemplative or transformational process of Book 1, therefore, describes a sort of spiral: in its end is a new beginning at a deeper starting point. The “perfect” disciple does not arrive at an Aristotelian perfection, to which no further good can be added, but to another threshold of the infinite, and is again faced with the need to enter once more into the renunciation which frees the heart for hearing the word of God (1.3).

At the end of the journey, then, we see that contemplative experience is not only the goal of the monastic quest or the possession of the “perfect”, but also its beginning, the first opening of the heart to the experience of grace and to the God who speaks to his disciples: it is always initiated by the God “who loved us first” (1 John 4:19). It begins again and again,

description of the crucified disciple (“[qui] presentia non contemplatur”), also dependent on Cassian, *Institutiones monasticae* 4.35; SC 109:174).

²⁴ I owe this insight to Ernest Larkin, “Carmelite Spirituality Today,” *Ascent* 1 (1965): 3–8; <http://carmelnet.org/larkin/larkino12.pdf>. Cf. Paul Chandler, *The Book of the First Monks: A Workbook* (Rome: Centro Internazionale S. Alberto, 1992); idem, “Reflections on The Ordinale of Sibert de Beka (1312),” in *We Sing a Hymn of Glory to the Lord: Preparing to Celebrate Seven Hundred Years of Sibert de Beka’s Ordinal 1312–2012: Proceedings of the Carmelite Liturgical Seminar, Rome, 6–8 July 2009*, ed. Kevin Alban, *Textus et Studia Historica Carmelitana*, vol. 32 (Rome: Edizioni Carmelitane, 2010), 104–5.

²⁵ Gregory the Great, *Moralia in Iob*, 30.9.33-35; CCSL 143:1514-15; PL 76:541B-543A. Isidore of Seville, *Etymologiae*, 12.7.43; PL 82:465A.

but not in the same place. Carmelite spirituality is revealed as an asceticism and mysticism of love which draws the person ever more deeply into the mystery of Christ.

From here on I must sketch some points only briefly.

2) *Contemplation takes place in the messianic community*

The *Liber de institutione* is structured by the medieval system of the four senses of sacred scripture, in which the literal or historical sense opens to the deeper spiritual or mystical senses.²⁶ Book 1 interprets its key biblical text in its mystical sense to reveal the spiritual journey of Elijah as a journey of transformation and to present him as the enduring example or pattern of monastic life. It is therefore a mode of mystical discourse. In the mystical meaning of the text the reader can find not only God's call to Elijah, but his own call as well. The text both hides and reveals the inner dynamic of religious vocation and of spiritual maturation.

Books 2-5 turn to the historical or literal meaning of the text: in doing as the Lord commanded, Elijah began a way of life which has been continued uninterrupted by his disciples, and the story of their institute is now told. The text thus switches to a historical mode of discourse, but nevertheless one with continuing spiritual purposes and content, in which the historical journey of the Order is also presented as a journey of transformation, an institutional counterpart of the transformation of the individual in Book 1. The transition from mystical interpretation in Book 1 to literal or historical interpretation in the following books is thus, I suggest, very tightly constructed. The sons of the prophets gathered by Elijah²⁷ find the fullness of their vocation in the coming of the Messiah, in their spiritual affinity with the Virgin Mary (Book 6), in their life and mission in the Christian community after their conversion (Book 5), and in their very openness to historical development (Book 7).

This mythical or symbolic-legendary history, defended by Carmelites as literal historical truth even into the 20th century, has been disparaged by critical readers since the 17th century and before.²⁸ However, in Ribot's telling it is rich and complex, and recapitulates the same contemplative values presented in Book 1, which are seen again and again, expressed in different ways and seen from different points of view. It is only possible here to pick out some aspects.

²⁶ Cf. Henri de Lubac, *Medieval Exegesis*, 3 vols, trans. Mark Sebanc and E.M. Macierowski, Ressourcement, (Grand Rapids, Mich.: Eerdmans, 1998–2007); David C. Steinmetz, "The Superiority of Pre-Critical Exegesis", *Theology Today* 37 (April 1980): 27–38.

²⁷ A theme not found in the Old Testament, where Elijah is a solitary figure and it is Elisha who is associated with the sons of the prophets. However, it was a common feature of medieval commentary, where Elijah is seen as the centre of a community of disciples, who live with him for 20 years or so on Mount Carmel. Cf. a more detailed treatment in Paul Chandler, "Princeps et exemplar Carmelitarum: the prophet Elijah in the *Liber de institutione primorum monachorum*," in *A Journey with Elijah: Carmelite Seminar on the Prophet Elijah. Whitefriars Hall, Washington DC, 3–9 April 1991*, ed. Paul Chandler, *Carisma e Spiritualità*, vol. 2 (Rome: Institutum Carmelitanum, 1991), 111–34.

²⁸ An English translator thought that most of the work "frankly does not merit the labour of translation"; Bede Edwards, *The Book of the Institution of the First Monks, Chapters 1–9*, Vineyard Series, vol. 3 (Boars Hill, Oxford: Teresian Press, 1969), ii. François de Sainte-Marie said much the same thing in his partial translation in *Les plus vieux textes du Carmel, La Vigne du Carmel*, vol. 32 (Paris: Editions du Seuil, 1944), 101. David Knowles dismissed the *Speculum Carmelitanum* of 1680, which has the *Liber de institutione* as its centrepiece, as "a comprehensive catalogue of the hoary legends that had received their *coup de grâce* in the *Acta [Sanctorum]*" in *Great Historical Enterprises* (London: Nelson, 1963), where he also documents the trouble Carmelite intransigence about their legends gave to the Bollandists.

Book 6 is Ribot's attempt to address a certain tension that arises from having both Elijah and Mary as the Order's patronal figures, together occupying the position usually taken by a single charismatic founder, lacking to the Carmelites. His solution is to propose a new interpretation of Elijah's vision from Mount Carmel of the little cloud rising from the sea (1 Kings 18.42-44).²⁹ Ribot, or his unknown source, interprets this event as a vision of the coming mother of the Messiah:

In the fact that Elijah's servant saw the little cloud arise from the sea, God revealed to Elijah that a certain girl child—that is blessed Mary, who is symbolised by the little cloud, and who is small like the cloud on account of her humility—would be born from sinful human nature, which is symbolised by the sea; and that the child at her birth would already be pure from every stain of sin, just as that little cloud arose from the bitter sea but without any bitterness. For although the cloud was originally of the same nature as the sea, yet it was of a different quality and a different property, for the sea is heavy and bitter, but that cloud was light and sweet (6.1).

To understand the interpretation of the cloud we must read with the Vulgate that it was “in the shape of a foot” (modern translations read “hand” with the Hebrew), or literally, rather, in the shape of “a human footprint” (*quasi vestigium hominis*). The mention of a footprint sets up a discourse of following or imitation. Elijah sees the Mary who is to come, and Mary is his follower, as he is hers: they are connected by voluntary virginity. She would be the first woman to practise consecrated virginity, as Elijah had been the first man.³⁰ As Jane Ackerman remarks, this Carmelite myth-making “almost completely suspends time”.³¹

In this way Ribot relates Mary and Elijah to one another at the level of the fundamental values of Carmelite spirituality—purity of heart, openness to the word, virginity and all it symbolises, orientation to the Saviour—and provides these dual figures with a spiritual unity and coherence which had not previously been satisfactorily achieved.

Elijah entrusts the secret of the coming of the Messiah to his followers, which they preserve through the centuries:

The mysteries of future events which that vision contained inwardly, beyond the narrative, and the great secrets which God revealed through it to the prostrate saint, Elijah deigned to unveil, not openly to all, but secretly to his companions.

²⁹The only antecedent I have found of Ribot's interpretation of the *nubecula parva* as a Marian symbol is a laconic comment of Hugh of Saint Cher: “In nubecula beata uirgo prefiguratur uel humanitas Christi” (In the cloud the Virgin is prefigured, or the humanity of Christ); *Repertorium apostillarum utriusque testamenti domini Hugonis cardinalis*, Basel: Amerbach, Petri, Koberger, 1504, vol. 1, f. 275. Emanuele Boaga and others have suggested patristic sources, but on examination they are not specifically related to the cloud of Elijah's vision on Mount Carmel. Even so, these references are in Greek writers largely unknown to the medieval West (Chrisippus of Cappadocia, Germanus I of Constantinople, Methodius of Olympus, *et al.*). For example, Cyril of Alexandria says that some see the cloud as a symbol of the body of the Saviour, others of the Virgin Mary, but he is commenting on the cloud of Isaiah 19:1, not 1 Kings 18; *Commentarius in Isaiam prophetam* 2.4; PG 70:451–452. Methodius of Olympus makes Elijah an imitator before the fact of Mary's virginity (Ribot has it the other way around), but without reference to the little cloud; *Sermo de Simeone et Anna*, 9; PG 18:371–372. See Emanuele Boaga, “Devotion to Our Lady at the Beginnings of Carmel,” in *Mother, Behold Your Son: Essays in Honor of Eamon Carroll, O.Carm.*, ed. Donald Buggert, Louis P. Rogge, and Michael J. Wastag (Washington, DC: Carmelite Institute, 2001), 90–91; cf. *Nello spirito e nella virtù di Elia: antologia di documenti e sussidi*, ed. Emanuele Boaga (Rome: Commissione internazionale carmelitana per lo studio del carisma e spiritualità, 1990), s.v.

³⁰That Elijah had been the first man to practise voluntary virginity is a patristic commonplace: Jerome (*Ep.* 22.21); Cassian (*Conl.* 21.4.2); Gregory the Great (*Hom.in Ev.* 2.29.6); Tertullian (*De monog.* 8); Isidore (*De off.* 2.18.1); cf. Hervé de l'Incarnation, “Élie chez les pères latins”, in *Élie le Prophète*, *Études Carmélitaines* (Paris: Desclée de Brouwer, 1955), 1:179-207.

³¹“Stories of Elijah and Medieval Carmelite Identity,” *History of Religions* 35 (1995): 144.

Handed down from them, we have the knowledge that under the form of the vision God revealed four great mysteries to Elijah at that time, which I will explain in order. First, that a certain girl child would be born who would come from her mother's womb pure of all sin. Second, the time when this would come to pass. Third, that this girl child would embrace perpetual virginity after the example of Elijah. Fourth, that God, joining his nature to human nature, would be born as a man of that virgin (6.1).

Rather than "slight diversions" indicating that Ribot "ran out of ideas"³² Books 6 and 7 are parts of a precise structure proceeding in a prismatic way: the fundamental spiritual qualities established in Book 1 are seen refracted again and again in different modes and from different points of view. Book 6 (on Mary) is a profound resolution of the tension involved in having both Mary and Elijah as the Order's foundational exemplary figures: they are now connected across the centuries and represent the same Christocentric way of life. In turn Book 7 (on the habit, an imitation of the first book of John Cassian's *Institutiones monasticae*), is not only a deliberate acknowledgement of the work's fundamental debt to Cassian, but also, in recounting the supposed change of cloak from white to striped to white again, it presents the habit not only as a token of the unchanging spiritual commitment of the monk, as in Cassian, but also presents its various forms as a token of change and institutional development.³³

In his unusual tale of Elijah's foreknowledge of the Virgin Mary Ribot thus makes the Old Testament sons of the prophets a messianic community, entrusted by their founder with a secret timetable for the coming of the Messiah. Thereafter they live through the centuries in longing, which will draw them to the Pentecost after the Resurrection, and this openness to the future is the context of their contemplation. Carmelite contemplation is thus shaped by expectation and longing: it is Christocentric in its focus and messianic in its hope for the future. It is an open-ended orientation to the infinite.

3) *Contemplation is practised in a liturgical community*

Ribot seems to have been aware of the anomalous character of an intentional community of prophets, for prophets are made by divine not human will (2.2, quoting 2 Peter 1:21). He notes, however, that not all prophets in the scriptures were foretellers of the future:

'David and the chief officers of the army separated for the ministry the sons of Asaph and Heman and Jeduthun, who prophesied with harps and psalteries and cymbals according to their number, serving in their appointed office'; and a little further on: 'Jeduthun prophesied with a harp over all who praise and thank God' (1 Chronicles 25:1, 3).

He therefore distinguishes between prophets in the full sense, those endowed by God with the power of foretelling the future, and those prophets instructed by Elijah in the *disciplina prophetica*, the singing of psalms:

Elijah established monks as his successors, not only to observe the monastic life according to the form given him by God but also to perform the office of prophesying: that is to sing psalms and songs and hymns devoutly to God, and to praise him not only with heart and tongue but also with musical instruments. This is the reason they were called prophets (that is, psalm-singers) and their life is called prophetic, that is, dedicated to singing psalms to the Lord with musical instruments (2.2).

³² Copsey, *Ten Books*, xiv, n. 19.

³³ The original striped cloak of the early Carmelites was, in fact, changed to white after a petition to Pope Nicholas IV in 1287; cf. Staring, *MCH*, 50–71.

In this way, Ribot makes the Old Testament ancestors of the Carmelites a liturgical community, dedicated like the friars to a discipline of community worship. Moreover, in a particularly profound touch, Ribot gives a contemplative and Christological character to his description of this worshipping community by adding a quotation from Gregory the Great (who of course postdates John of Jerusalem, the putative author of the *Liber de institutione*; this is one of Ribot's specifically noted interpolations):

For when the voice of psalmody is set in motion through the intention of the heart, a way is prepared by means of it for almighty God to come into the heart, that he may infuse into the attentive mind either the mysteries of prophecy or the grace of devotion. Therefore it is written, 'The sacrifice of praise will honour me, and there is the way by which I will show him the salvation of God' (Psalm 49:23). Now 'salvation' in Latin is 'Jesus' in Hebrew. Therefore, in the sacrifice of praise is made a way of revelation in Jesus, because while devotion is infused through the psalmody, a way is made for us in the heart by which we come at last to Jesus. As he himself says when he is speaking about making himself known, 'Whoever loves me will be loved by my Father, and I will love him and show myself to him' (John 14:21). For this reason it is also written, 'Sing to the Lord, say a psalm to his name, make a path for him who rises above the heavens; the Lord is his name' (Psalm 67:5). Certainly he rises above the heavens who trampled death by his rising. When we sing to him we make a path that he might come to our heart and set us afire with the grace of his love (2.3).³⁴

The liturgical worship of the Carmelites is thus presented as a form of contemplation, a receptivity to the Risen One who comes as transforming love to the open heart. The themes, or better the dynamic, of book 1 are once again briefly recapitulated in a prismatic way that suggests the contemplative aspect of all the activities of life, culminating in worship.

4) Contemplation creates a community of peace and justice

The Carmelites' quixotic attempt to construct a continuous history for themselves on Mount Carmel from the 8th century BC faced numerous historical obstacles, including the discontinuity of the Babylonian exile of Israel. For Ribot, however, the peaceful life of the sons of the prophets insulates them from the turbulence of history.

In Book 3, and especially 3.5, Ribot constructs a picture of the Elijan community on Mount Carmel where all are united in the pursuit of purity of heart and where unity and peace in community are produced through the practice of silence, harmony and daily worship. It is the utopia of the Carmelites, whose reality is vouched for by biblical authority:

What we have said above about them and their place, the prophet Isaiah foretold speaking in the person of the Lord, 'Judgement shall dwell in the wilderness, and justice shall sit in Carmel, and the work of justice shall be peace, and the service of justice, quietness, and security forever. And my people shall sit in the beauty of peace, and in the tabernacles of confidence, and in wealthy rest' (Isaiah 32:16-18 [Vulgate]). See here how beautifully and systematically the Prophet describes their good life, to be imitated by Carmelite monks after them (3.5).

In interpreting these verses, Ribot notes among other things the precisely contemplative dimension of the harmonious community, in another recapitulation of the themes of Book 1:

Commending their life, the Lord foretold of them all, 'And my people shall sit in the beauty of peace', that is internal, 'and in the tabernacles of confidence', that is of obtaining the joy of celestial glory, 'and in wealthy rest' of mind, that is from the taste and contemplation of the delights proceeding from 'the torrent of the divine pleasure' (Psalm 35:9) (3.5).

³⁴ Cf. Gregory the Great, *Homiliae in Hiezechielem Prophetam*, 1.14; ed. M. Adriaen, *Corpus Christianorum Series Latina*, vol. 142 (Brepols: Turnhout, 1971), 12-13.

He returns to this theme in 4.7, after the account of the ascension of Elijah, to explain why Carmelites were not taken into captivity in Babylon with the rest of Israel:

Indeed those monks were so disposed to one another by their peacefulness that there was no fighting among them; and their mouths were so fortified by quietness that there was no excessive talking among them; and they were so quiet and secure in their hearts, that their hearts did not reproach them before God (cf. 1 John 3:21). Therefore, trusting in the protection of God, whose wishes they always sought to fulfill, they had no fear about enemies. As the Wise Man says, ‘When the ways of people please the Lord, it converts even their enemies to peace’ (Proverbs 16:7). Therefore, because they were striving to please God by their justice, God protected them from fear and the attacks of their enemies and from the captivity of the Jews, as he had promised when he said, ‘And my people will sit in the beauty of peace, and in the tabernacles of confidence, and in wealthy rest’, namely in the virtues and abundant pastures of the doctrine of true devotion (4.7).

It is striking here that being “disposed to one another” is a fruit of what one might call contemplative virtues, of sensitivity and receptiveness, peacefulness of heart, quietness, disciplined speech. *Ad intra*, this very reserve creates a space for the other; *ad extra* it disarms the hostility of enemies. Their justice is not only “righteousness” but an alternative social order springing from contemplative values and practices.

5) *Contemplation is insight into the biblical word*

Another large obstacle in the construction of Carmelite mythology was the challenge of transforming a community of Old Testament prophets into a Christian community. This Ribot does by inventing an ingenious story about their presence in Jerusalem at Pentecost, where they heard the preaching of the apostles and were converted. Their presence is attested by scripture itself, for does not St Peter address them specifically in Acts 3:25, saying “You are the sons of the prophets”?

They now live the Christian life: “perservering in the teaching of the apostles and in the communion of the breaking of bread, with one accord they continued daily in prayer in the temple, praising God with gladness and simplicity of heart” (cf. Acts 2:42, 46). Many preach Christ in Phoenicia and Palestine (5.8).

This is the ending point of the “history” of the sons of the prophets. The quotation of Acts 2 should be seen, I think, as an important literary inclusion. The story which started with an Old Testament command which led Elijah to found the community of prophets now ends with a New Testament text central to the self-understanding of the new religious movements of the 12th century and their heirs in the 13th: the ideal of the *vita apostolica* and of the Jerusalem community, the *ecclesiae primitivae forma*.³⁵

Some readers have found the *Liber de institutione* a conservative or reactionary work, expressing a critique of mendicancy and a preference for the eremitical life.³⁶ However, I believe this interpretation misses the dynamic nature of this “history” as a story of

³⁵ See Marie-Humbert Vicaire, *L'imitation des apôtres: moines, chanoines et mendiants, IVe-XIIIe siècles*, Tradition et Spiritualité, vol. 2 (Paris: Éditions du Cerf, 1963); M.-D. Chenu, *Nature, Man, and Society in the Twelfth Century: Essays on New Theological Perspectives in the Latin West*, ed. & trans. Jerome Taylor and Lester K. Little (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1968); Giles Constable, “Eremitical Forms of Monastic Life,” in *Istituzioni monastiche e istituzioni canonicali in Occidente 1123–1215*, Atti della settima Settimana internazionale di studio, Mendola 28 agosto–3 settembre 1977 (Milan: Vita e Pensiero, 1982), 239–64; and Giovanni Miccoli, “*Ecclesiae primitivae forma*,” in *Chiesa gregoriana: ricerche sulla riforma del secolo XI*, Storici antichi e moderni, N.S. vol 17 (Florence: La Nuova Italia, 1996), 225–99.

³⁶ Jill R. Webster, *Carmel in Medieval Catalonia*, The Medieval Mediterranean: People, Economies and Cultures, 400–1453, vol. 23 (Leiden: Brill, 1999), 81–88.

institutional transformation: Jews become Christian, prophets become apostles, hermits become preachers, the sons of the prophets become Carmelites. In the long duration of their history they were hermit-monks, but in the direction of their history they are destined for the mendicant life of friars. Where Book 1 recounted the inner transformation of the person, Books 2-5 recount the historical transformation of the institution to which they belong.

This transformation not only has a contemplative dimension, but in fact is opened up to them by the contemplative receptivity to the word of God which has characterised their journey since its first step (1.3):

Every moment of the day was spent in exercises of study and teaching of the holy gospel. They also pursued the interpretation of the holy books, considering the laws of the fathers in allegorical interpretation. For the whole of the Old Law seemed to them similar to an animal, in that externally, like a body, it had the letter itself and the things which the literal meaning signifies; but inwardly, like a soul, within the letter lay hidden the invisible and spiritual sense of what might be called a profound and divine mystery. Taught this meaning by the apostles, contemplating it in a more sublime and lofty way as in a mirror, and drawing certain marvelous meanings from the very names of the letters, they were filled as from a lavish banquet with the divine and profound wisdom of the holy books (5.8).

Contemplation is here a process of *lectio divina*, of entering into the unfolding mystery of divine revelation, in which not only the word of God is opened up, but also oneself. Conversion comes through hearing and encountering the living, transforming word of God; the new life in Christ is deepened and nourished in meditation on the word, in which the Spirit guides the Christian to understand the hidden mystery revealed and fulfilled in Christ. Here is yet another recapitulation: the contemplative journey of individual and institution begins again and again in openness to the Word, in being-addressed-by-God.

6) *Contemplation overflows in ministry*

Finally many of them, pouring out to others what they had drawn from the apostles, preached the faith of Christ throughout Phoenicia and Palestine, spreading the doctrines of the faith, and witnessing to the most honourable church of God by the character of their life and monastic practice (5.8).

Apart from two added quotations, these are the concluding words of the “history” of the Elijan institute, and should be read as a clear allusion to the Carmelites’ adoption of the mendicant ideal and an argument that it was a natural fulfillment of their eremitical foundation. This took place with the revision of the original Rule by commissioners appointed by Innocent IV in 1247, which allowed the hermits to transition from a strictly eremitical life to pastoral work in the cities.³⁷

In the background to the *Liber de institutione*’s presentation of this development is the apostolic quality of many versions of the medieval eremitical life, surprising in its diversity, and often enough characterised by itinerant preaching, here seen as already foreshadowed in

³⁷ Cf. Cicconetti, *La Regola*, esp. 183–298. It is one of the ironies of Carmelite history that our only reliable account of the pre-1247 Rule and the process of its revision is from the great myth-maker, Felip Ribot.

the apostolic age.³⁸ Even in 3.7 the sons of the prophets sometimes visit towns to preach and heal. Although the vocabulary of the work is monastic (the earliest Carmelites are regularly called *monachi*) the dynamic of their history is already directed towards their transformation into friars, who seek to preach the Gospel and so be of pastoral usefulness, *sibi et proximis proficere*.³⁹ Thus the events of the 13th century by which they adopted an urban and apostolic life engaged in preaching and the *cura animarum*—partly the result of papal policy towards eremitical groups—are, in Ribot’s vision, already foreshadowed in antiquity.⁴⁰

In these chapters particularly, Ribot’s work connects with the genre of *apologiae* for mendicant life, sparked in the 13th century by the criticisms associated especially with William of Saint Amour, and in the 14th by the campaign headed by Richard Fitzralph.⁴¹

7) *Contemplation discerns the signs of the times*

I believe Emanuele Boaga will treat this theme more fully, so I just refer to it briefly. The *Chronicle* attributed to William of Sandwich recounts the story of how the Carmelites first came to leave the Holy Land, beginning in the 1230s and ’40s (9.3).⁴² Some of the weaker brothers (*infirmiores*), terrified (*conturbati et perterriti*) by the incursions of the Saracens, wished to leave the Holy Land and return home (possibly breaking their vow of life-long

³⁸ Among a large literature on hermits and preaching see, for example, G. Meersseman, “Eremitismo e predicazione itinerante dei secoli XI e XII”, in *L’eremitismo in occidente nei secoli XI e XII: atti della seconda settimana internazionale di studio, Mendola, 30 agosto-6 settembre 1962*, Milano: Vita e Pensiero, 1965, 164–179; Antonio Vuolo, “Monachesimo riformato e predicazione: la Vita di san Giovanni da Matera (sec. XII)”, *Studi medievali* ser.3, 27:1 (1986): 69–121; George Piero Ferzoco, “Preaching by Thirteenth-Century Italian Hermits”, in *Medieval Monastic Preaching*, ed. Carolyn Muessig, Brill’s Studies in Intellectual History vol. 90, (Leiden: Brill, 1998), 145–159.

³⁹ Cf. Cicconetti, *La Regola*, 195–200; and Innocent IV, bull *Paganorum incursus*, 27 July 1246, ed. Adrianus Staring, “Four Bulls of Innocent IV: A Critical Edition,” *Carmelus* 27 (1980): 281–82.

⁴⁰ On the papal preference for pastoral ministry see, for example, Brenda M. Bolton, “Via Ascetica: A Papal Quandary,” in *Monks, Hermits and the Ascetic Tradition: Papers Read at the 1984 Summer Meeting and the 1985 Winter Meeting of the Ecclesiastical History Society*, ed. W.J. Sheils (Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1985), 161–91; Franco Dal Pino, “Papato e ordini mendicanti-apostolici ‘minori’ nel duecento,” in *Il papato duecentesco e gli ordini mendicanti: Atti del XXV convegno internazionale, Assisi 13–14 febbraio 1998*, Atti dei convegni della Società internazionale di studi francescani e del Centro interuniversitario di studi francescani, 8 nuova ser. (Spoleto: Centro italiano di studi sull’alto Medioevo, 1998), 107–59.

⁴¹ Penn R. Szittyá, *The Antifraternal Tradition in Medieval Literature* (Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 1986); Guy Geltner, “William of St Amour’s *De periculis novissimorum temporum*: A False Start to Medieval Antifraternalism?”, in *Defenders and Critics of Franciscan Life: Essays in Honour of John V. Fleming*, ed. by Michael F. Cusato and Guy Geltner, *The Medieval Franciscans*, 6 (Leiden: Brill, 2009), pp. 105–118; James D. Dawson, “Richard FitzRalph and the Fourteenth-Century Poverty Controversies”, *Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 34 (1983): 315–344. On the response of the friars see especially Edward A. Synan, “Bonaventure and Aquinas on Monks and Friars”, in *Roma Magistra Mundi: Itineraria Culturae Medievalis. Mélanges offerts à Père L.E. Boyle à l’occasion de son 75e anniversaire*, ed. Jacqueline Hamesse, Fédération Internationale des Instituts d’Etudes Médiévales, 10/1–3 (Louvain-la-Neuve: Fédération Internationale des Instituts d’Etudes Médiévales, 1998), 2:885–899; Decima L. Douie, “St Bonaventura’s Part in the Conflict between Seculars and Mendicants at Paris”, in *S. Bonaventura, 2: De vita, mente, fontibus et operibus s. Bonaventurae*, ed. J.G. Bougerol (Grottaferrata: Collegio s. Bonaventura, 1974), 585–612.

⁴² William attended the general chapter of 1287 as provincial of the Holy Land; *Acta Capitulum Generalium Ordinis Fratrum B.V.M. de Monte Carmelo*, ed. Gabriel Wessels (Rome: Curia Generalitia, 1912), 1:10. See also Keith J. Egan, “An Essay Toward a Historiography of the Origin of the Carmelite Province in England,” *Carmelus* 19 (1972): 67–100, at 79–83.

pilgrimage without return, *ad propria nunquam reversurus*)⁴³ and found monasteries elsewhere. Other members of the community insist that it is irrevocably tied to the Holy Land.⁴⁴

The opposing positions are submitted to a process of discernment by the community (*in consilio*) by examining the scriptures and the founding tradition of the Order, and the conclusion is reached that the teaching and example of Christ, and the example of Elijah, allow the departure. For Christ said, “If you are persecuted in one town, flee to another” (Matthew 10:23), and he did this himself in fleeing the Holy Land for Egypt when persecuted by Herod; and Elijah also quit the Holy Land for Horeb when persecuted by Jezebel. The prior of Mount Carmel, considering these reasons, and being reassured by the Virgin Mary in a dream, gives them permission to leave and make foundations elsewhere.

This account is rich in elements to consider: a problem is evaluated by the community in the light of the examples of Christ and the founder of the Order; opinions are changed; a substantial adaptation is approved, despite its unlikely origin with the weaker members of the group; it is confirmed for the prior in a dream, a symbol of a mysterious grace at work; and finally enacted by the authority of the prior, to whom each has vowed obedience according to the Rule. Adaptation and change are guided by a contemplative discernment process, based in a communal listening to the word of God.

Conclusion

As I have remarked above, these are merely sketches or hypotheses about the qualities of contemplation in the *Decem libri*. I am conscious that they are not firmly based on any clear definition of contemplation and, in fact, use the term in a possibly unstable way. However, the few uses of the semantic field *contemplatio* in the *Decem libri* make it difficult to fashion a precise formulation of how the concept is understood there and few verbal reference points. Nevertheless, the very tight construction of the work, in which the same themes are constantly recapitulated in varied but coherent ways, seems to offer some control of interpretation. I offer these points for further consideration, contradiction, or elaboration.

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⁴³ On which see Cicconetti, *La Regola*, 72–77, 466–67.

⁴⁴ My opinion, contrary to the scholarly consensus, is that the *Chronicle*, even if it has been substantially reworked by Ribot, is not his fabrication but preserves some genuine memories of the Carmelites in the Holy Land, even of the 1230s or '40s, if not some fragments of an authentic work by William or some other. With Cicconetti (*La Regola*, 466) I think it extremely unlikely that any Carmelite in the 1370s, when the Order was once more suffering severe criticism, would invent a story which explained the migration of the Carmelites to Europe and the origin of their mendicantisation as the result of the terrors, and possibly the vow-breaking, of the weakest of their members.

I find the argument, advanced most strongly by Richard Copsey, that Ribot must be the author of the whole of the *Decem libri* because its components appear to have been known to no-one but himself both inconclusive and inconsistent (*Ten Books*, xiii-xiv). Taken to its logical conclusion, it would require that we reject the text of the pre-1247 “Albertine” Rule, for which Ribot is the only witness, but it is universally and for good reason accepted as authentic. It would also require that we attribute to him Book 1, which is generally recognised, also by Copsey, as being an independent work from a non-Carmelite source, even though it is otherwise entirely unknown.

I am conscious that I am not making here any conclusive argument about multiple authorship in the *Decem libri*. I merely wish to question the current assumption that Ribot is the undoubted fabricator of the whole and to re-open the issue for discussion and investigation.